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Khudoykulova D.P.

Head of the Public Health College named after Abu Ali bin Sino

**MORPHOLOGY OF THE ENDOTHELIUM OF THE LYMPHATIC
CAPILLARIES OF THE PERITONEUM AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP
TO THE MESOTHELIUM**

Annotation: morphological features of the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the peritoneum covering the anterior, superior and posterior abdominal walls, it can be noted that most numerous large and small argyrophilic inclusions in the cytoplasm of cells are found in the endothelium of the capillaries of the parietal peritoneum. Thus, the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the parietal and visceral peritoneum has its own morphological features due to the function and structure of the peritoneum covering the organ.

Key words: Endothelium, peritoneum, lymphocapillaries.

The endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries play an important role in metabolism. This explains the interest shown by morphologists in the endothelium of capillaries, which is a biological membrane through which blood and lymph are separated from parenchyma cells and the main substance of the connective tissue. In 16 dogs, we examined the endothelium of the lymphatic vessels of the peritoneum in its various sections on 86 macro-microscopic preparations. The data of our studies indicate that in dogs, as in humans, the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the peritoneum has a cellular structure with a large polymorphism. In the dog, the endothelial cells of the lymphatic capillaries are stellate or polygonal in shape, usually the stellate cells are wide, but sometimes they change and become polygonal in shape, where the

length prevails over the width. The size of the endothelial cells of the lymphatic capillaries in dogs is 100x120, 120x90, 130x90 microns. In dogs, in some preparations of the peritoneum covering the anterior wall of the abdomen, there were places in the endothelium a break in the cell boundaries. In the cells of the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the studied dogs, as in humans, free argyrophilic inclusions are observed point (1-3 microns) and larger (5-10 microns) in the form of light fields with a dark rim. They are scattered throughout the cytoplasm of cells in dogs. The nuclei are oval and round, depending on the shape of the cells. The structural features of the peritoneum in animals are also reflected in their lymphatic system. The lymphatic capillaries of the peritoneum of the anterior abdominal wall lie at a depth of 15-17 microns. and in some places up to 35 microns. In the peritoneum covering the diaphragm, they are located more superficially at a depth of 4-12 microns, sometimes adjacent directly to the mesothelium. Peritoneal mesothelial cells are smaller in size than the corresponding endothelial cells of lymphatic capillaries, their structure is more stable. The size of the mesothelial cells of the peritoneum of the anterior abdominal wall in a dog is 40x50, 30x25, 40x40 microns. Cells are usually wide, but there are also narrow ones. Their shape is different: more often polygonal, cubic or oval (the peritoneum covering the front wall of the dog's abdomen). In a dog, two types of cells are also observed in the peritoneum covering the anterior wall of the abdomen: some have a brown cytoplasm and light nuclei, while others have a light yellow granular cytoplasm and dark nuclei. In mesothelial cells, where the cytoplasm is darker, there are larger nuclei. Along the argyrophilic boundaries of mesothelial cells, expansions are observed in the form of grains or rings with enlightenment in the center. The cytoplasm of mammalian mesothelial cells often contains argyrophilic inclusions. They can be larger (4-8 microns), like in a cat or smaller - in a dog they lie in the cytoplasm in the form of grains (1-2 microns.) The endothelial cells of the lymphatic capillaries of the parietal and visceral peritoneum are

characterized by high polymorphism. Endothelial cells are closed, but sometimes there are breaks in them. On the preparations obtained, we observe the discontinuity of cell boundaries, which were combined with multiple argyrophilic inclusions in the cytoplasm: when the cell boundaries were closed, the number of inclusions decreased. Based on the analysis of the results of the study, it can be assumed that environmental factors, and primarily the nature of nutrition, affect the intensity of metabolism and lead to functional and morphological changes in the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries. If we compare the morphological features of the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the peritoneum covering the anterior, upper and posterior abdominal walls, it can be noted that the most numerous large and small argyrophilic inclusions in the cytoplasm of cells are found in the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the parietal peritoneum covering the diaphragm. In the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the parietal peritoneum, which covers the posterior wall of the abdominal cavity, inclusions are also numerous, but smaller than in the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the diaphragmatic peritoneum. In the cytoplasm of the cells of the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the peritoneum covering the anterior wall of the abdomen, argyrophilic inclusions in the cytoplasm of the cells are predominantly small and few, they rarely contain large inclusions in the form of light yellow fields with a dark rim. The structure of the parietal and visceral peritoneum has its own characteristics, since the connective tissue that is part of the peritoneum is different in different places. These features of the structure of the connective tissue of the peritoneum are also reflected in the morphological properties of the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries. Thus, the endothelium of the lymphatic capillaries of the parietal visceral peritoneum has its own morphological features, determined by the function and structure of the peritoneum covering the organ.

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